

The Role Of Work Behavior Systems And Job Satisfaction By Integrating Organizational Commitments And Expertise Innovation: An Asian Perspective

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Abstract

This empirical study contributes to the literature by examining the relationship between Affective Commitment, innovation work skills, continuum commitment and work behavior, job satisfaction simultaneously and positively from the Asian perspective. The findings reveal that continuum commitment and skills/abilities have a significant effect on work behavior, affective commitment, continuum commitment, and work ability. Work behavior do not have a significant effect on job satisfaction and affective commitment does not have a significant effect on work behavior. The findings and analysis of the structural equation model of Amos and SPSS Version 25 which is the end user consisting of 185 (one hundred and eighty-five) respondents in Eastern Indonesia, Asian. This research adds new insights to the extant literature and provides implications for research and practice satisfaction. future work in Eastern Indonesia, Asean.

Introduction

Studies related to organizational commitment & work behavior are very interesting, because today's open competition requires optimal work behavior in order to create high performance and further job satisfaction is obtained. Problems in private and government organizations are closely related to organizational commitment and scientific studies in the international world have been carried out which are very supportive in order to develop organizational commitment, Ambarwati (2018), Sjamsuddin & Firmansyah Fadhilah (2018), Brahmawati & Suprayetno (2008), Carolita & Rahardjo (2012), in order to develop and improve employee work behavior which will have an impact on performance as well as (i) Affective commitment which is identical with the strong desire of a person to continue working for the organization, because it is in line with his desire or work loyalty Munajah Anwar & Debora Purba (2018), Tobing (2009), Palupi (2013). (ii) Innovation of expertise that is identical to individual characteristics, in this case organizational members whose performance and loyalty are high towards the organization and have an impact on organizational success. Fauzi, Dimas (2019), Subyantoro (2014). (iii) Continuous commitment as a sense of trust in organizational values, loyalty and involvement of an employee to the organization will have an impact on work behavior and performance, so that it will be needed for organizations for company excellence Murty and Hudiwinarsih (2012), Wahyudi (2012). In the application of theory and its development regarding affection commitment, expertise /ability and continuity commitment, there is still a weak level of development of employee pride in the context of company service, there is still a need for fostering employee loyalty levels, still lacking levels of improvement and comfort as well as company working conditions, still lacking understanding the importance of anticipating rapid and permanent changes in organizational management processes. Some solution steps are: (i) Management emphasizes more on the importance of the level of customer satisfaction and loyalty (ii) Management should apply open, professional and visionary management in order to create pride in the company in the context of service. (iii) In order to increase incessant measures and anticipation of changes that are very fast and unexpected. (iv) Organizational commitment is an important part of the company, because there is an interrelated relationship with work behavior & job satisfaction.

Evaluation of some of the results about the importance of steps that can increase organizational commitment, skills / abilities & work behavior are (i) As a form of employee emotional attachment to the organization, so that it will increase work behavior, job satisfaction & employee job loyalty to the organization. (ii) Employees who are more satisfied with their management with an increase in their fair performance by feeling that their welfare is considered, will directly increase the high organizational commitment. (iii) High commitment to the company will increase hard work and better work behavior for the company, so that employees will have the spirit to defend their organization. (iv) With a high commitment to the company, with striving to improve work behavior

& achievement work and have a definite belief to realize the company's goals. Research on developing levels of organizational commitment, innovation in skills and work behavior of employees in Indonesia contributes to developing organizational studies in the context of decentralization of local government (i) The application of organizational commitment theory, innovation skills and work behavior has been implemented during the implementation of government decentralization (ii) Related to research which is still limited both in quality and quantity when developed countries have been intensively implementing it. (iii). Organizational commitment as a part related to the company is very important in efforts to improve work behavior & performance in order to achieve global company satisfaction, now it has become part of the public's desire as a need. Ambarwati, Crisna et al (2018), Palupi (2013). Thus, it will be the main concern for research and development in Asian, then whether the development of organizational commitment according to the initial theory can be implemented or can follow the progress that has been achieved which is very rapid at this time. Current research is to provide a solution to how the level of organizational commitment, innovation in ability and work behavior & satisfaction contribute positively to companies in Indonesia.

2. Methodology

The target population of this study was 185 (one hundred and eighty-five) respondents of PLTU company employees. The data were collected through a questionnaire during the period March 2019 to February 2020 using the Structural Equational Model (SEM), which requires the total sample size to be five to ten times the number of observations for each parameter Ferdinand (2006). The relationship between constructs is described in a theoretical framework. A five-point Likert-type scale (1-strongly disagree: to strongly agree) was applied throughout the questionnaire. Factor loading is used to evaluate discriminant validity where only items with a factor load exceeding 0.50 will remain in the model (Ferdinand et al., 2006).

2.2 Identification of Research Variables

Job satisfaction as an endogenous construct is measured by four dimensions: job satisfaction (KP1), emotional factor (KP2), ease of obtaining products (KP3), product quality (KP4). Adapted from the work of Sitingjak (2008) and work behavior with four dimensions: social dimensions (PK1), vocational skills (PK2), work motivation (PK3), initiative confidence (PK4) adapted from Griffiths (2004). On the other hand, the exogenous variable affective commitment is measured by norms (KA1), routine work (KA2), priority (KA3) adapted from Robbin and Judge (2011). Innovation skills are assessed by Knowledge (IK1), Skills (IK2), Satisfaction (IK3), Ideas (IK4) adapted from Arief Subyanto (2014). Sustainable commitment is assessed by asset security (KK1), company loss (KK2), profit in the company (KK3) adapted from the work of Robbin and Judge et al. (2011).

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework of research variables affects Y1 and Y2

Reliability testing is used to determine the consistency of research measuring instruments, so that the measuring instrument can be trusted if it is used more than once. The reliability and validity test with the calculation of the results of regression weights, the AVE value has a value exceeding the loading ≥ 0.5 and the CR value has ≥ 0.7 , so that if it exceeds the value 0.5 and 0.7 which means that overall, all variables have met the validity and reliability. The normality test is carried out using a critical ratio value of ± 2.58 at a significance level of 0.01% (Ghozali, 2004) and that means the assumption of normality is fulfilled and feasible for further use. The research data is said to have outliers if the p1 and p2 values are less than 5% and the data containing outliers can affect the normality of a data. The existence of multicollinearity and singularity can be seen through the covariance matrix values which are really small or close to zero. The confirmatory factor analysis test for these variables showed a collision of variables with a factor value of ≤ 0.05 , meaning that these variables were significant in contributing to forming latent variables. Model modification was carried out according to software modification suggestions (modification indices), namely connecting several constructs with covariance lines so that there was a relationship between constructs. If the Good of Fit (GOF) Index resulting from the Cut Off Value from the Modified Research Model does not meet the GOF, then the model must be modified so that all indices meet the specified criteria. Hypothesis testing was carried out by observing the CR and Sig values of the studied variables based on the maximum likelihood estimates by looking at the regression weights table, which is

said to have a significant effect if the CR value of the variable is ≥ 1.96 and the probability < 0.001 . Test the correlation to determine the strength and direction of the relationship between variables. Meanwhile, to determine the magnitude of the effect caused by a variable on other variables how much it contributes to the effect test. For scoring the answers to the questionnaire using a Likert scale. Sugiyono (2005), Likert scale is used to measure attitudes, opinions and perceptions of a person or group of people about social phenomena. With the help of observing the value of CR and Sig. The variables studied were based on the maximum likelihood estimates by looking at regression weights, seven hypotheses were tested, which are; (i) Sustainable commitment is positively related to Behavior; (ii) Affective commitment is positively related to behavior; (iii) Innovation ability is positively related to behavior; (iv) Continuous commitment is positively related to satisfaction; (v) Innovation of expertise is positively related to satisfaction; (vi) Continuous commitment is positively related to satisfaction; and (vii) Behavior is positively related to satisfaction.

3. RESEARCH RESULTS

3.1 Overview of Respondents

Based on the results of field data collection, through collection of answers obtained from 185 selected respondents, proving the implementation of job satisfaction in terms of commitment, expertise makes a significant and positive impact on work behavior and leads to employee job satisfaction.

3.2 Testing the Validity and Reliability of the Construction

Validity test by calculating AVE and CR where AVE is ≥ 0.5 , then the construct is said to be valid and the CR value is ≥ 0.7 , then it is said to be reliable as the research results. According to Gullford's (1956) criteria in Widodo (2006), the reliability coefficient ranges from 0 to 1, the closer to 1, the more reliable the instrument is. While the opinion of Nugroho (2000), the variable is said to be good if it has a Cronbach's Alpha value > 0.60 . In exploratory research, reliability between 0.5-0.6 is acceptable. (Nunnally and Bernstein: 1994).

3.3 Normality Test.

The normality test was performed using a critical ratio value of ± 2.58 at the 0.01% significance level. Ghazali (2006). The results of the normality and linearity test research show that all indicators have a value of CR not exceeding 2.58 so that the research data is fulfilled. Meanwhile, the research data is said to have outliers if the p1 and p2 values are less than 5% and the data containing outliers will affect the normality of a data. From the results of the outlier test on the research data, it was found that 32 p1 data had an outlier value < 0.05 . To obtain normal research data, all data containing outliers must be excluded for further SEM analysis. The result of SEM analysis contained 136 data whose values were more than > 0.05 , so the results were said to be normal.

3.4 Structural Equation Modeling

Index models that still do not meet the GOF, so they are modified to meet the criteria. Modification of the model is to connect several constructs with covariance lines so that there is a relationship between constructs, so that according to the Goodness of Fit criteria, it is required as follows: From the table below shows the goodness index of fit. Post-evaluation, it was found that all goodness of fit tests showed good results and that the model was in accordance with the data. Solomon, Ashmore, & Longo (1992). Thus, according to theory and supported by facts, it means that the model is the best to explain the relationship between variables.

3.5 Hypothesis Testing

The effect test was carried out by observing the CR and Sig values of the studied variables based on the maximum likelihood estimates by looking at the regression weights table, which is said to have a significant effect if the CR value of the variable is ≥ 1.96 and the probability is < 0.000 . As shown in the following table: Correlation test is conducted to determine the strength and direction of the relationship between variables. In this study, there are 6 correlations between variables that are correlated. (Attachment). Based on the table, it can be seen that the variable relationship between reward -quality and quality - promotion is the largest correlation compared to the relationship between other variables. To determine the magnitude of the effect caused by a variable on other variables, the total efficiency test was carried out with the results according to the following table:

Table 1 Total Effect Test

	Komitkon	Innovation Expertise	Komitaf	Behavior	Satisfaction
Behavior	0.452	0.261	0.004	0	0
Satisfaction	0.432	0.282	0.189	0	0

Note: Komitkon = Continuum Commitment; Komitaf = Affective Commitment

Based on the test results the total effect of the above, it appears that the variable *Komitkon* is the variable with the largest contribution in giving effect to the product variable Behavior (0.452) and Satisfaction (0.432), compared with other variables such as Expertise, and Commitment.

4. Discussion

- (i) The influence of affective organizational commitment factors on work behavior. From the results of the study, the Affective Commitment Factor which has indicators of pride in the organization, loyalty,

company norms, the presence of emotional ties, and promotion at the company, and involvement in work have no significant effect on work behavior with a CR value of 0.022 smaller likelihood estimates of one comma. nine six and probability 0.031 smaller 0.05. This shows that the affective organizational commitment variable is not accepted, meaning that work behavior is not influenced by the commitment variable indicator dimensions above. These results are in conjunction with previous research that organizational commitment has a negative effect on behavior (2019). These results are not in line with previous studies such as Sjamsuddin (2018), Majang Palupi (2013), that affective organizational commitment has a strong effect on job satisfaction and retaliation behavior in the workplace, Rivai & Junani Sagala (2011). This result is different from previous research such as Windy Aprilia Murty & Gunasti Hudiwinarsih (2012), that organizational commitment has a significant effect on employee performance. These results are in line with the theories about organizational commitment that organizational commitment can improve work behavior. According to (Ivan Aris Setiawan & Ghozali, 2006: 193). Organizational commitment is a "behavioral perspective where commitment is defined as behavior that is consistent with activity (consistency line of activity)".

- (ii) The influence of the expertise innovation factor with four dimensions, namely work knowledge, job skills, job satisfaction and a preference for certain ideas. Subyantoro et al. (2014) is significant, which means acceptance of the hypothesis on work behavior. This means that behavior is influenced by the dimensions of the individual's characteristics, in other words, changes in behavior are caused by expertise on these four dimensions. This is not in accordance with the research of Murty & Hudiwinarsih (2012). Research shows that work involvement has a negative effect on Alkusani's work behavior (2019). This result is not different from the results of Fauzi's (2019) research that individual characteristics have an effect on performance. ERW. Wahyudi (2012), shows that there is a significant influence on work performance.
- (iii) The effect of the continuous organizational commitment factor. As for the dimensions of the indicator are protecting emotional assets, will not move to another organization because there is no other choice, working in a company is indeed a necessity, but the company has not been able to promise a good future that has no significant effect on work behavior. These results are in accordance with the research of Alkurnani & Sukaris et al., (2019), Murty and Hudiwinarsih et al., (2012), Rachmawati et al., (2007). This study is different from the research conducted by Brahmasari & Suprayetno et al (2008), and Carolita & Rahardjo et al (2012); that organizational commitment affects the quality of audit results and is also different from the theories of Meyer et al (1990), Porter et al (1991: 295) and Mathis & Jackson (2001) which state that organizational commitment is a means to improve work behavior or performance.
- (iv) The factor of organizational commitment in terms of the dimension of protecting company assets, will not move to another organization, feeling that they are profitable in their own organization is not positively related to job satisfaction. This is different from, Sariningtyas & Sulistiyani (2016). Sjamsuddin, FF. et al (2018) Organizational commitment has a positive relationship with satisfaction.
- (v) The ability innovation variables in terms of work knowledge, job skills, job satisfaction and liking for certain ideas are not positively related to satisfaction. This means that satisfaction is not caused by these four dimensions, influenced by other variables. In contrast to the results of research by Sariningtyas, ERW & Sulistiyani. Et al (2016).
- (vi) Affective organizational commitment variable has no positive relationship with satisfaction in terms of the dimensions of company norms, routine and full day work and company promotion. In contrast to the results of Sjamsuddin, FF et al (2018).
- (vii) Behavioral factors are not significantly related to satisfaction in terms of social relationships, vocational expertise, work motivation and initiative & self-confidence, meaning that satisfaction is determined by other factors. In contrast to the results of Suriningtyas, ERW & Sulistiyani et al (2016) characteristics have a positive relationship with satisfaction.

5. Conclusions

According to the research results it can be **concluded** as follows:

- 1) (i) Work behavior is not influenced by the variable affective organizational commitment in terms of the dimensions of indicators of organizational pride, loyalty, job satisfaction, organizational citizenship behavior, emotional ties, regular and full day work, organizational priorities and involvement in organizations. (ii) Work behavior is influenced by individual characteristics in the form of expertise innovation with indicators of work knowledge, work skills, job satisfaction and a preference for certain ideas. (iii) Work behavior is influenced by continuous organizational commitment with the indicator dimension of protecting company assets, will not move to the organization another, feeling fortunate in one's own organization with a better future. (iv) Job satisfaction is not influenced by the continual commitment variable with the dimensions of the indicator of protecting assets, feelings, feeling loss if leaving

the company and feeling that it is fortunate to be organized by itself. (v). Job satisfaction is not influenced by individual characteristics with the indicator dimensions of knowledge, skills, satisfaction and ideas. (vi) Satisfaction is not influenced by the variable affective commitment in terms of dimensions of indicators of company norms, routine and full in the company and priorities. (vii) Satisfaction is not influenced by behavioral variables in terms of the dimensions of social relationship indicators, vocational skills, work motivation, and initial confidence.

- 2) **In terms of the contribution of research to the development of science:** An application of a good theory may not necessarily be implemented according to the original theory, for the Indonesian situation it should adapt to local conditions and situations.
- 3) **Delivery of research limitations**
 - (i) This study has several limitations, the result of which is the lack of the research that of the four companies it is expected that only one will allow it to be the object of research, so that the number of respondents studied is limited. Measurement of data using a questionnaire whose answer accuracy is highly dependent on the opinion of each & / the willingness and ability of the respondent, the lack of cooperation between the company as an object of research in terms of researchers getting information about the data they have, so that the research results cannot be published more optimally in order to improve work productivity and employee development & training.
 - (ii) This study has limitations in data generalization, because this study is in accordance with existing variables or in accordance with existing objects.
 - (iii) Whereas data measurement uses a questionnaire whose answer accuracy is highly dependent on the opinion of each individual and the willingness and ability of the respondent, in addition to the questionnaire the use of the questionnaire for respondents' participation is rather low. Combining the questionnaire with the interview will result in a higher level of answer accuracy, although this method requires a longer time.
- 4) **Suggestions for future researchers.** In this study, in order to obtain significant results, a good theory is not necessarily applicable in Indonesian conditions. For further researchers, quantitative and qualitative methods can be done to research with different variables or different locations and the instrument is not only in the form of a questionnaire, it can also be done directly with the interviewees, so that the results obtained are more accurate, and there is no perception (view). different between respondents and researchers.

Table 2 Goodness of Fit test

Goodness of Fit (GOF) Index	Cut Off Value	Modified Research Model	Model Evaluation
Chi Square	Kecil	92.406	Small
Probability	≥ 0.05	0.955	Good
RMSEA	≤ 0.080	0.000	Good
GFI	≥ 0.9	0.936	Good
AGFI	≥ 0.9	0.972	Good
TLI	≥ 0.95	1.432	Good
CFI	≥ 0.95	1.000	Good

Resource: Processed from the results of the evaluation of the 2020 good of fit criteria.

Table 3 Effect Test Results
(Regression Weights-Maximum Likelihood Estimates)

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Conclusion
Behavior	<---	Komitkon	0.452	0.209	2.159	0.031*)	Reject H0
Behavior	<---	Komitaf	0.004	0.171	0.022	0.982	Reject H0
Behavior	<---	Innovation Expertise	0.491	0.2277	2.469	0.024*	Reject H0
Satisfaction	<---	Komitkon	3.532	77.894	0.045	0.964	Accept H0
Satisfaction	<---	Innovation Expertise	0.072	45.029	0.046	0.963	Accept H0
Satisfaction	<---	Komitaf	0.215	1.653	0.13	0.896	Accept H0
Satisfaction	<---	Behavior	-6.865	173.414	-0.04	0.968	Accept H0

Note: Reject Ho = If P Di < 0.05 and value CR ≥ 1.96

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